

Studies on Ylides : Synthesis of Some new *p*-Iodosubstituted Stilbenes

R. S. TEWARI*, N. KUMARI, P. S. KENDURKAR and K. C. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpure-208 002

Manuscript received 19 September 1977, revised 17 April 1978, accepted 7 July 1978

A series of new *p*-iodosubstituted stilbenes have been synthesized by the interaction of *p*-iodobenzylidenetriphenylphosphorane, a new semistabilized phosphonium ylide with a range of mono- and disubstituted benzaldehydes. The structures of the products are based on IR and NMR spectral evidences.

THE reaction of phosphonium ylide with carbonyl compounds has proved to be a unique method for the conversion of carbonyl function into an olefinic double bond because of its structural specificity¹. During the course of our investigations²⁻¹⁰ on a programme directed towards utilization of the ylides as an olefinating reagent, we have presently synthesized a series of new *p*-iodosubstituted stilbenes by the reaction of *p*-iodobenzylidenetriphenylphosphorane (I), a new semistabilized phosphonium ylide, with a range of aromatic aldehydes.

Reaction of triphenylphosphine with *p*-iodobenzyl bromide in benzene gave *p*-iodobenzyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (II) in good yield. Treatment of this salt (II) with sodium methoxide in methanol generated an intense yellow coloration due to formation of ylide (I) which on subsequent reactions with a series of mono- and disubstituted benzaldehydes at room temperature gave *trans-p*-iodosubstituted stilbenes (IIIa-j) (Scheme 1) in appreciable yields.

SCHEME 1

Similarly the reaction of ylide (I) with terephthaldehyde was also successful at room temperature to give *trans*-1, 4-*bis* (4-iodostyryl) benzene (IIIj).

All the *trans-p*-iodosubstituted stilbenes (Table 1), most of them are new, were obtained almost exclusively *trans*-isomers and no *cis*-isomer was detected. It gave correct elemental analysis. The IR, UV and NMR spectral data were also consistent with that expected for *trans*-isomers¹¹ (Table 2).

The IR spectra (KBr) of the *trans*-stilbenes (IIIa-j) showed absorptions at 1625-1580 cm⁻¹ ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$) and at 976 cm⁻¹, the latter are associated with out-of-plane deformations of hydrogen attached to *trans*-olefinic system¹². The UV spectra (ethanol) for *trans*-substituted stilbenes (IIIa-j) showed characteristic bands (λ_{max}) at 295-342 m μ . The NMR spectra (CDCl₃) exhibited *trans* olefinic protons, in the range of δ 6.65-7.40 (d, J=16.4-16.8 Hz) and aromatic protons at δ 7.00-7.92 ppm.

Experimental

Preparation of *p*-Iodobenzyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (II)

A solution of 10.48 g (0.04 mole) of triphenyl phosphine and 11.88 g (0.04 mole) of *p*-iodobenzyl bromide in 400 ml of anhyd. benzene was heated under reflux on a steam bath for 3 hrs. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool at room temperature to give a white crystalline solid which was separated by filtration and recrystallized from methanol-benzene (1 : 4) to give white crystals of new *p*-iodobenzyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (II) in 70% yield. m. p. 256-57°. Found : C, 53.65 ; H, 3.73 ; C₂₅H₂₁BrIP requires : C, 53.64 ; H, 3.75%. IR spectrum (KBr) 1005, 1450 cm⁻¹ (ν P-aryl), 725 cm⁻¹ (ν P-alkyl). NMR (CDCl₃) δ 6.80-8.05 (19H, aromatic, multiplet), δ 5.44 (2H, CH₂, doublet J_{PH} = 15 cps).

Preparation of trans-p-Iodosubstituted stilbenes (IIIa-j): To a stirred suspension of *p*-iodobenzylidenetriphenylphosphorane (I), generated from 2.23 g

* To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

(0.004 mole) of salt(II) and sodium methoxide (0.004 mole) in 100 ml of methanol, was added, under nitrogen, 0.004 mole of aromatic aldehyde. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 6 hrs. The resulting precipitate was collected, washed with

water, dried and purified by crystallization from appropriate solvent or by chromatographic separation to yield *trans-p*-iodosubstituted stilbenes (IIIa-j) (Table 1).

TABLE-1. *trans-p*-IODOSUBSTITUTED STILBENES

Product	Ar	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C)	Recryst. solvent	Analytical Data	
					Found%	Calcd.%
ArCH = CHC ₆ H ₄ . I-(<i>p</i>)						
(IIIa-j)						
III a	C ₆ H ₄	55	148-49†	CHCl ₃ -hexane	74.69	3.58
III b	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	58	204-05	„	74.70	3.59
III c	3-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	67	86-87	EtOH (80%)	53.56	3.88
III d	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	72	212-13	C ₆ H ₆ -Hexane	53.57	3.86
III e	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	68	209-10	AcOH	53.53	3.85
III f	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	47	133-34	EtOH	53.57	3.86
III g	3,4-(OCH ₂ O)C ₆ H ₃	65	154-55	CHCl ₃ -Hexane	53.54	3.84
III h	2,4-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	75	120-21	Benzene-Hexane	53.57	3.86
III i	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	85	113-15*	EtOH (90%)	56.23	4.02
III j	4-I.C ₆ H ₄ CH = CHC ₆ H ₄	51	252-53	Xylene	56.25	4.06
					52.44	4.02
					52.45	4.09
					57.43	3.13
					57.43	3.14
					44.79	2.39
					44.80	2.40
					47.83	2.82
					47.86	2.84
					49.40	2.96

†, Lit.¹³ m.p. 152° ; *, Lit.¹³, m.p. 110°

TABLE-2. SPECTRAL DATA OF *trans-p*-IODOSUBSTITUTED STILBENES

Compound	IR data (KBr) cm ⁻¹		U.V. (Ethanol) λ _{max} , nm	¹ H-NMR data (CDCl ₃) δ (ppm)
	νC=C stretching	νC-H* deformn.		
III a	1585	970	324	7.16 (d, J=16.5 Hz, 1H, Ha), 6.72 (d, J=16.4 Hz, 1H, Hb), 7.25-8.10 (m, 9H, ArH)
III b			295	
III c	1600	970	299	3.85 (s, 3H, OCH ₃), 7.26 (d, J=16.8 Hz, 1H, Ha), 6.86 (d, J=16.6 Hz, 1H, Hb), 7.32-7.86 (m, 8H, ArH).
III d			342	3.82 (s, 3H, OCH ₃), 7.18 (d, J=16.6 Hz, 1H, Ha), 6.75 (d, J=16.6 Hz, 1H, Hb), 7.25-7.72 (m, 8H, ArH).
III e	1625	978	314	3.68 (s, 3H, OCH ₃), 7.09 (d, J=16.4 Hz, 1H, Ha), 6.64 (d, J=16.5 Hz, 1H, Hb), 7.08-7.92 (m, 8H, ArH)
III f			335	
III g	1620	970	316	5.93 (s, 2H, O ₂ CH ₂), 7.02 (d, J=16.7 Hz, 1H, Ha), 6.65 (d, J=16.5 Hz, 1H, Hb), 7.00-7.68 (m, 7H, ArH)
III h	1585	968	308	7.40 (d, J=16.6 Hz, 1H, Ha), 6.95 (d, J=16.6 Hz, 1H, Hb), 7.37-7.94 (m, 9H, ArH).
III i			305	

s = Singlet d = doublet, m = multiplet

*Out of plane deformations of hydrogen attached to the carbon carbon double bond.

Acknowledgements

The authors wish to thank Dr. S. D. Shukla, Director, Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur, for the facilities, one of authors (KCG) thanks U. G. C., New Delhi for the award of Teacher Fellowship.

References

1. A. W. JOHNSON, "Ylide Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1966, p. 132.
2. R. S. TEWARI and P. S. KENDURKAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 415.
3. P. S. KENDURKAR and R. S. TEWARI, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1973, 28b, 475.
4. R. S. TEWARI, N. KUMARI and P. S. KENDURKAR, *J. Chem. Engg. Data*, 1976, 21, 125.
5. P. S. KENDURKAR and R. S. TEWARI, *J. Organometallic Chem.*, 1973, 60, 247; 1975, 85, 173.
6. R. S. TEWARI and K. C. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14B, 419, 829.
7. R. S. TEWARI and K. C. GUPTA, *J. Chem. Eng. Data.*, 1978, 23, 93.
8. R. S. TEWARI, K. C. GUPTA and S. C. CHATURVEDI, *Z. Naturforsch.* 1977, 32b, 1165.
9. R. S. TEWARI and S. C. CHATURVEDI, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1977, 3843.
10. R. S. TEWARI and K. C. GUPTA, *Syn. Comm.* 1978, 8 315.
11. H. GUSTEN and M. SALZWEDEL, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 173.
12. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley, New York, 1954, p. 31.
13. P. PFEIFFER H. SCHMITZ and T. INOME, *J. Pract., Chem.*, 1921, 70, 121.